

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 – Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.10 Annual report on external communications for impact assessment April 2019- March 2020

Lead contributor	Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot (39 – Sanofi Aventis R&D)
Other contributors	Agnes Kant (9 – Stichting Lareb) Linda Harmark (9 - Stichting Lareb) Michael Steel (38 – Novartis Pharma AG)

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	18 Mar 2020	Draft for review
V1.0	1 Apr 2020	Final

Abstract

The main aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality and harmonisation of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicine use in pregnancy and during breastfeeding.

The objective of this report is to summarize communication actions performed in WP5 to disseminate knowledge about medicine use during pregnancy and lactation and to engage pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem between April 2019 and March 2020. The communications actions may have different targets and different messages.

For this report on the first year of the project, the main communication activities were related to the importance of information on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding and to engage HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women or general public to participate in our survey collecting end user needs. In addition, some activities were performed to increase awareness of the ConcePTION project although this does not fall within the scope of WP5.

Methods

The objective of the report is to make an inventory of communication actions performed in WP5 on the first year of the project.

The communication actions are classified by their objective:

- Increase awareness on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding
- Engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem

The communications actions are grouped by objective and are described using the following parameters:

- the geographical reach
- the target audience
- the channel used
- the date of dissemination
- the main presenter

Results

The communication actions for this report are divided into two main groups:

- General information actions with different channel
- Engagement actions

The communications actions on ConcePTION project to increase awareness on medicine use in pregnancy or breastfeeding have been conducted by WP5 leads by face-to-face interactions with teratology specialists and an interview in a magazine for pharmacovigilance specialists.

Table 1: General communication actions to increase awareness on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Europe	Teratology Specialists	Face to Face interaction (ENTIS annual meeting)	Sept-2019	Agnes Kant, Ida Niklson
World	Pharmacovigilance specialists	Print magazine (Uppsala report issue 81)	Oct-2019	Agnes Kant, Mats Hansson

Actions to engage stakeholders to participate in a survey about end user's information needs during pregnancy and breastfeeding were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations. Communication materials were developed together with the ConcePTION communication task force.

Table 2: Communication actions to engage stakeholders to participate into the survey

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Netherlands	General public	Social media	Oct-2019	Agnes Kant (Lareb)
Sweden	HCPs	Face to Face interaction	Oct-2019	Ulrika Nörby (SCC)
Europe	General public	Webpage (ConcePTION)	Oct-2019	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	MCIP database	e-mail	Jan-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	Flavia Bustreo (WHO, GaviBoard, PMNCH)	Social media	Jan-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
Sweden	HCPs and the public	Web page (Janusmed)	Feb-2020	Ulrika Nörby (SCC)
World	Organization UN - Phumzile Mlambo	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	NGO - Maternity Worldwide	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	NGO - Every Mother Counts	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
Netherlands	General public	Social media	Feb-2020	Agnes Kant (Iareb)
World	MCIP database	e-mail	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)

UK	Charity - HGSupportUK	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
UK	Charity, Nurse - HGSupportUK - Spewing Mummy	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
UK	Association - AIMS	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	Organisation WHO - Regions for Health	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	NGO - Expecting Health	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
Canada	Patient - CAPA_arthritis - Laurie Proulx	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	Midwifery - MidwiferyToday	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
UK	Midwifery - Midwivesmag	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
UK	Midwifery - MidwivesRCM	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
US	Midwifery - SagefemmeSB	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	Midwifery - Caring Midwives	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	KOL - Toyin Saraki	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	Midwifery - The International Confederation of Midwives (ICM)	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
UK	The RCN	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
France	General public	Social media	Feb-2020	Annie Druet-Cabanac (Sanofi)
US	Midwives Alliance	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	WeMidwives	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	all4maternity	Social media	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	UNFPA (Petra van ten Hoope Bender)	1-1 call	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics	1-1 Call	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)
World	La Leche League International	1-1 Call	Feb-2020	Helena Harnik (Synergist)

Discussion and Conclusion

In the first year of the project, the communication efforts were mainly about the ConcePTION project as a whole and activities related to the surveys that WP5 had to gain input about end users information needs about medicine use during pregnancy and breastfeeding. The two surveys had 500 and more than 2100 participants, respectively, showing that the communication, mainly through web and social media channels is a successful way to reach the target group with a low budget.

Collaboration and coordination with the ConcePTION communication task force works well, and support has been received from the task force in creating and implementing communication messages.